

‘Personal Style’: design for the embodied, lived aesthetics of use, rather than the inert, aesthetics of artefacts.

Fiona Jane Candy, Department of Design, Faculty of Design and Technology, University of Central Lancashire, UK. +44 1772 893368 fjcandy@uclan.ac.uk

Christopher James Edmundson, Department of Technology, Faculty of Design and Technology, University of Central Lancashire, UK. +44 1772 893317 cjedmundson@uclan.ac.uk

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Abstract This paper reports on an ongoing collaboration between fashion design and sports science, which is exploring the potential of a ‘personal style device’ (PSD): an artefact/interaction concept that can be worn on the body and be sensitive to the kinematics of wearing it. We aim that such a device will have the potential to stimulate new forms of body skill and personal movement in the context of fashion and everyday social performance. The project is influenced by work in other disciplines: philosophy, sociology, anthropology, material culture, fashion theory, neurophysiology, human computer interaction, games design and dance. It draws on techniques of record and analysis from biomechanics and sports science e.g. the use of accelerometers, 3D video, gait analysis, motion capture, pressure mapping and force distribution, which all have the potential to facilitate input and output of qualitative movement data. This paper establishes our research context and design strategy.

Keywords affect, body, identity, movement, social, style

1. Introduction

Human bodies are dressed bodies; all cultures that we know of dress the body in some way, through clothing, tattooing, body painting or other forms of embellishment or adornment (Polhemus, 1998). As both a personal and social medium, dress brings valuable insight into the ways that people interact with each other in an increasingly complex social world. Yet this is still so often overlooked in practical studies of embodiment, where the body in action is portrayed as an impersonal diagram or as a stylized nude whose cultural nuance or idiosyncratic movement is difficult to document. A residual misconception exists within some fields informing design e.g. ergonomics, anthropometrics, wearable technology, of human bodies as generic, unemotional, skeletal apparatus, requiring ‘tools’ to adapt or extend their function. There is a possibility that an under-estimation of the significance of dress, and an over-commitment to the aesthetics of *artefacts*, rather than the embodied aesthetics of people *using* artefacts, has meant that many designers overlook the subtly personalised behaviour of wearing and use.

In contrast, our project’s focus is the intangible, fashioning synergy that is manifested during the interaction of the individual and artefact e.g. demeanour, character, bearing, stance, poise, persona, gait, cadence, gesture. Our premise is that it is the *dressed body*; an animated, social entity, that communicates identity to others, not the clothing artefacts alone. ‘Dress works on the body, imbuing it with social meaning, while the body is a dynamic field that gives life and fullness to dress’ (Entwistle and Wilson, 1998). We are aware of developments within the growing field of movement-based interaction: within games e.g. EyeToyⁱ or Dance Dance Revolutionⁱⁱ; and within immersive art environments and performance (e.g. Moen, 2005; Shiphorst and Anderson, 2002; Reeves et al, 2005). We are also influenced by the emergence of new aesthetic movement forms like le parkourⁱⁱⁱ and free running that by bridging dance, athletics and sport, stimulate possibilities for design that can appeal to novel combinations of the senses.

In order to more fully communicate our research context, this paper will first connect research in design with related ideas about the body, identity and sociality within other disciplines: e.g. fashion theory, sociology, anthropology, material culture, psychology and neurophysiology. The body’s structure and functional anatomy are then briefly discussed in relation to propulsion. In

order to indicate practical parallels between dress and the wider sphere of design and emotion, we take a look at some examples of existing artefacts that can be categorized as having an affecting relationship with movement style and emotions of identity. Several methods from biomechanics are reviewed for their potential to capture and input qualitative movement and the authors construct a feasibility matrix relating to output mediums. We then draw from the information presented throughout, to devise a design strategy for a ‘personal style device’: an interaction concept worn on the body that can emulate clothing’s affect and stimulate movement style and demeanour. This is currently proposed in the context of ‘fashion’ and everyday social performance, although future applications within sport, movement rehabilitation and therapy contexts are also envisioned. We use the term ‘dress’ to describe the practice of dressing in and wearing clothing, but also of carrying and using other forms of personal artefacts in close proximity to the body as expressions of sociality and identity. We define ‘personal style’ as the effect of artefacts on the qualitative movement of their wearers (and subsequently on the perceptions of identity made by spectators). The authors propose that developing a greater understanding of ‘fashioned’ bodies, including the relationship between the kinesics of wearing/using artefacts and the neurophysiologic workings of ‘sense of self’, may help designers to better understand how human bodies move and feel as individuals, but also as social beings.

2. Sense of Self

A combination of ideas gathered from several disciplines can contribute to an understanding of how we are conscious of our bodies and how this awareness convenes emotions of identity or style. The following sub-sections refer to some of these ideas and aim to stimulate consideration of their implications for design.

2.1 Proprioception and Kinesthesia

Proprioception, which literally means ‘sense of self’, is how neuroscientists refer to the sensory information system that allows us to perform movements and to be aware of where our body is and what it is doing. Kinesthesia defines the sensing of motion, weight, or position of the body, as muscles, tendons and joints move; this is also referred to as ‘muscle sense’ or as ‘muscle memory’ (Blom and Chaplin, 1988). The volume of sensory information received by the brain is enormous: it comes via the eyes, but also from the muscles, joints, tendons, skin and vestibular

system. The brain copes with all this hierarchically. It has learnt to ignore the signals that it is used to, like the stretching of skin during walking, or the sensation of the soles of the feet touching the ground, so these signals are handled within the unconscious parts of the brain, lower down in the system. Information only reaches the higher or conscious parts of the system when the experience is new or unexpected (Damassio, 2000) and so people tend to lose consciousness of various types of regularly encountered external feedback, such as how their clothing feels when it is worn. However, lack of consciousness may not mean lack of affect.

2.2 Potentiality for Action

Recent empirical developments in neuroscience e.g. the use of MRI and the study of brain or limb damage, have encouraged hybrid, cross-disciplinary interpretations of the ways that emotions of self are experienced in our minds but also through our bodies. From his perspective in psychology, Bermudez writes about self-consciousness and that proprioception ‘provides a way, perhaps the most primitive way, of registering the boundary between self and non-self’; and that it ‘gives us a sense not just of the embodied self as spatially extended and bounded, but also as a potentiality for action’ (Bermudez, 1999).

2.3 Kinesthetic Materiality

The way that dress may work on the sensual body and how this in turn mediates experience of the self, is implied by Entwistle (2000) when she contextualizes Eco’s description of wearing a pair of jeans for the first time since losing weight. The jeans are still too tight and he describes how they *feel*, how they pinch and restrict his movement and make him very aware of the lower half of his body. He describes this experience as “epidermic self-awareness” and explains that he had not felt it before: *“As a result, I lived in the knowledge that I had jeans on; whereas normally we live forgetting we are wearing undershorts or trousers. I lived for my jeans and as a result I assumed an exterior behaviour of one who wears jeans. In any case I assumed a demeanour...Not only did the garment impose a demeanour on me; by focusing my attention on demeanour it obliged me to live towards the exterior world.”* [Ibid.] Perhaps contemporary science would refer to Eco’s “epidermic self-awareness” as haptic or as kinesthesia, but his account vividly conveys awareness of a *fashioned* self.

2.4 Garment Design and ‘Le Porté’

In a recent interview, Dior’s menswear designer Slimane, described his approach to garment design: *“For me, it’s so much about the way people wear clothes, the way they behave, not so much about the clothes themselves. In France, it’s called le porté. It’s a very old-school way of dressing based on how the clothes fall on the body. I work on this natural level of understanding clothes. It comes from getting so into my own world and chasing my own moods. I pay attention to movement, the way the clothes translate on the body, even the way they translate to a girl.”* (Carter, 2005). Slimane’s account of method seems to imply that everyday observation of people, knowledge of the properties of cloth and the techniques of garment cutting and making, combine to form an empathic system for understanding emotional and postural schema and how the body moves through space. Design for clothing involves the ways garments function, encompass, adorn and differentiate body shape, but also how they prompt styles of movement via the translation of kinesthetic materiality (cloth, cut, fit, position of pockets and other garment details sensed by the body) into corporeal performance. Slimane’s reference to “le porté” reminds us that the human body is a dressed, sensual entity: carried through space in fashioned ways that choreograph gender, act out individuality and affiliation, exhibit skill and animate identity.

2.5 Personal Creativity v Social Constraint

For many people, dressing is often more about concealing anxiety about what to wear, than about explicit displays of creativity (Woodward, 2005). Making decisions about how to dress for social interaction draws on personal creativity but also on social constraint. The proximity to the body and to notions of the self inherent in the medium of dress, means that external factors cannot remain abstract: they are brought within the realm of the intimate and may be experienced as an internal quandary or ambivalence (Wilson 1984). In normal or habitual circumstances we experience clothing as an extension of the body, as a second skin. But when social mores shift or environment changes, or when dressed in a new or less familiar way (like Eco in his jeans), our clothing impacts cognitively on our minds, but also via skin and muscle sensors to reawaken our attentiveness to the possibilities and limitations of embodiment. Anthropologists Banerjee and Miller have shown through their ethnography of the sari that when interpreted as ‘systems of thinking about the world’, our clothing also has to ‘feel right’. (Banerjee and Miller, 2003).

2.6 Habitus and Techniques of the Body

The sociologist Bourdieu refers to taste (i.e. aesthetic discernment) and its relationship with the body as the body schema: ‘which is the depository of a whole world view and a whole philosophy of the person and the body’ (Bourdieu, 1984). He articulates his concept of the *habitus* as a set of dispositions that the body learns intuitively through social interaction and that it can use given the right social context. This includes styles of dressing and moving. Bourdieu has argued that the schemes of the habitus and related ‘techniques of the body’, may ‘function below the level of consciousness and language, beyond the reach of introspective scrutiny or control of the will’ (1984 i), but also that they have significant impact on our systems of aesthetics and social capital. For example, the way a particular group or class may physically carry themselves i.e. through their demeanour or bearing, provides other people with an understanding of who they are. Although Bourdieu’s ideas revolve primarily around power and social reproduction, the habitus brings a means to consider sense of self; the ways it is expressed via the body and its social implications.

2.7 Dynamically Embodied Action

Within anthropology, studies of human movement have undergone a paradigmatic shift from an observationist view of ‘behaviour’ grounded in kinesics and proxemics, to the conception of the action sign and an understanding of body movement as ‘dynamically embodied action’ (Farnell, 1999). For example, Farnell’s field research explores the use of the “handshake” amongst Native Americans and reveals how important aspects of identity are conveyed through qualities of touch (Farnell, 1995). She shows how the misuse of glossed terms like “handshake” have concealed distinct action signs and their meanings, and how identity is experienced and communicated via all of the body’s senses.

If we bring together these various components of ‘sense of self’: epidermic self-awareness; proprioception and kinesthesia; awareness of a potentiality for action; the socially reproductive implications of habitus; the concept of dynamically embodied action, *le porté* and the material propensities of clothing, then we begin to reveal links between the senses and society.

Neurophysiologic processes like proprioception or kinesthesia may be elemental not only in the

physical, functional apparatus of *how* our bodies work, but also in the phenomenological experiences of self and identity that underpin *who* we are.

3. Functional Anatomy and Propulsion

For the purpose of observing movement, this section briefly visits anatomy in order to gain a better understanding of the kinematics of propulsion. The body can be divided into two main units: upper and lower. The upper unit is comprised of head/neck; chest/upper spine; shoulder joint/scapula; arm/forearm/wrist/ hand/ fingers. It essentially serves exploring, manipulating, gesturing activities. It initiates and extends reach space, communicates through spatial gesture, body touch, grasp, enveloping, dispersing, and intertwining. The lower unit is comprised of lower back/lower abdomen; pelvis/hip/thigh/ lower leg/foot/toes. This unit is initiator of the centre of weight and essentially serves locomotor activity (the transports of body weight) and postural changes (the support of body weight). In addition, the observer sees the body as two halves; right and left and/or as trunk plus segments (Bartenieff and Lewis,1997).

In most activities that produce propulsion via a foot-ground interface the knee and hip extensors are the predominant muscle groups activated. Movement is initiated by the spinal rotators with the main sources of power being provided by the muscles surrounding the pelvis (Gracovetsky, 1988). The mono-articulate vastus group act as energy generators in extending the knee, while the rectus femoris acts mainly as an energy distributor by controlling knee extension and transferring energy from the hip joint to the knee joint (Cavanagh and Lafortune, 1985; Zajac, 2002). The gluteus maximus is a powerful hip extensor, which works in unison with the semi-membranosus, semi-tendinosus, and biceps femoris muscles of the hamstrings. The bi-articulate nature of the hamstring group means they can act both as hip extensors and knee flexors. They thus control the speed and magnitude of knee extension by transferring energy to the hip joint, and act as knee flexors when the net knee joint torque is flexor (Cavanagh and Lafortune, 1985; Zajac, 2002). They are also able to produce a greater moment at the hip joint than the quadriceps and thus together with the gluteus maximus create a net hip joint extensor moment. Although not contributing greatly to bipedal locomotion, the gastrocnemius and soleus muscles must be able to develop sufficient tension to transfer the energy generated by the powerful hip and knee extensors to the ground (Zajac, 2002).

Functional anatomy details how propulsion and kinesthetic awareness of self is sensed and enacted using a network of interconnected muscle groups, some of which are more powerful or dynamic than others. Their synchronous complexity allows a seemingly infinite range of nuanced movements.

4. Movement Style and Emotions of Identity

Everyday dress involves many types of artefacts that are implicated in movement style as a primary or secondary effect of use. The following are brief case studies of artefacts that can be categorized as having an affecting relationship with body movement and identity.

4.1 Cigarettes

Although now out of fashion in much of the West, cigarettes have an affecting relationship with demeanour. Smoking a cigarette can be incorporated into the emotional cadence of body style in many different ways: from grandiose, languid movements to the staccato or furtive.

Figure 1, cigarette smoking and body style.

Smokers hold the generic white stick with different combinations of fingers and thumb (e.g. Figure 1), but whole body posture or poise can be affected as a cigarette becomes part of the smoker's body schema and conveys complex, tacit information about the identity of individual smokers to spectators.

4.2 Jeans

As a version of trousers, denim jeans are strongly implicated in stance and movement, as they clothe the supporting, propelling limbs that join us to the ground. The classic jeans demeanour is manifested through the hanging or hooking of hands on to and into the pockets, or through the belt loops, which by providing resting opportunities for the hands can help to relax the shoulders and upper body. There are several nuanced versions of gait depending on the jeans' cut and which can relate to specific fashion cultures. Jeans' stance and demeanour gives off an air of easy readiness (Figure 2), where *casual* refers to a style of clothing but also to the postural schema of its wearers, particularly in comparison to stricter forms of body control of the past. Prior ethnographic research has included video interviews with jeans wearers, which captured wearers' hands touching and interacting with garments, styles of stance and movement, along with verbal accounts of clothing strategies (Candy, 2005).

Figure 2, examples of jeans stance, from *The Body Dictionary* (Candy, 2005)

These interviews revealed that people can have strong views on how jeans may be worn convincingly, although are generally better able to describe how/when jeans look wrong, like wearing the waist too high, too low, or an unflattering cut; than how they look good. These opinions were often expressed via qualitative interpretations of the identity of the wearer: i.e. *how* you wear your jeans can be *who* you are in terms of others' assessments of social identity and cultural currency.

4.3 Trekking/Walking Sticks

Recently, many lovers of the outdoors have adopted a new style device; the high-tech walking stick. These new sticks (or ‘poles’) are adjustable in height, have impact absorbing functionality, are light but strong with carbide tips and pack away telescopically for ease of storage.

Figure 3, the embodied identity of trekkers.

Unlike crook handled walking sticks that are associated with the support of frailty or disability, these sticks have vertical, soft touch rubber handgrips and the empowering, streamlined appearance of a ski stick. In use, the stick is swung forwards with the hand and wrist until the tip anchors in the ground, and then pulled back with tricep and bicep, creating a sense of levering the land closer. Users can augment their balance by leaning their weight onto it for rest, or for additional support and traction when in adverse terrain. Advertised by their manufacturers to lessen impact on the joints, burn more calories and increase oxygen consumption^{iv}, sticks also heighten users’ awareness of the interconnected rhythms of walking: arm swing and stride. These ‘fashionable’ sticks bring emphasis to the resolute, intrepid body style of trekkers (Figure 3).

We hope we have shown through these few examples, that interaction between the body and everyday clothing and other personal objects can create styles of movement that affect emotions of self (and vice versa) and subsequently the assessments of identity made by spectators.

5. Capturing Movement Data

The next section reviews methods available within biomechanics that can capture the subtle, qualitative movement data relating to wearing and use.

5.1 Input: Biomechanical Analysis

Biomechanical analysis equipment in the sporting context is used almost entirely to obtain quantitative kinematics and kinetic data about an athlete or group of athletes in order to either improve performance or decrease the chance of injury. Since athletes who compete in top level competition are often separated by tenths, hundredths, and even thousandths of a second it is important that the equipment used to measure the parameters of the athlete are extremely sensitive and accurate. Thus sports biomechanics by its nature is a highly refined and specific discipline that makes use of complex engineering, electronics, and mathematical modelling (Cappozzo *et al.*, In Press). The possibilities of using this equipment to measure demeanour, bearing, character, poise or gesture, are at the opposite end of a spectrum. This is to such an extent that the social implications of the terms mentioned above are rarely, if ever, mentioned in biomechanical dialogue. Although any sports scientist would agree that some elite athletes are 'poetry in motion' and are wonderful to watch because of how gracefully and fluidly they move, seemingly wasting no effort and appearing to float, actually measuring and isolating these subtle movements is one frustrating and difficult area of biomechanics (Hall, 1999; Cappozzo *et al.* In Press). It is important to be aware of what biomechanical equipment can and cannot measure, and as a result only some of the tools normally used are relevant and applicable to the quantification of individual movement styles.

Goniometers, and increasingly more commonly electric goniometers, used to measure angular motion and velocities, are one method used to assess human movement and gait (Chantelot *et al.*, 1998), usually by means of potentiometers (Trew and Everett, 2001). Accelerometers are also used to measure displacement and energy used (e.g. Knight *et al.*, 2004), and global positioning systems (GPS) can be used for notional analysis of general human movement (eg Luinge and Veltink, 2004).

In a similar way that someone's finger print is unique, an individual will have his or her own unique foot strike pattern, as measured by all three orthogonal directions – vertical, anterior-posterior, and medial-lateral.

Figure 4, foot sensors and pressure distribution. Tekscan.^v

It must be pointed out that although the foot strike pattern is unique, it is not unchangeable, and in the case of the medial-lateral force component, is not always repeatable (Cavanagh and LaFortune, 1980; Bates *et al.*, 1983; Hamil *et al.*, 1984; Cavanagh, 1990; Grabiner, 1993). For example footwear, ground surface, the foot-ground interface, orthotics, and speed of movement will all alter the force-time curve 'pattern'. However in general the way someone moves can be quantified by the changes in ground reaction force data, turning moments and the resulting centre of pressure path. Foot-pressure sensors can be used in a similar way (Figure 4), with the advantage that pressure distribution over the whole of the foot can be measured (Chen and Bates, 2000).

Motion analysis using two-dimensional video cameras or three dimensional infra-red motion capture is the obvious first choice to the biomechanist in order to quantify human kinematics (Cappozzo *et al.*, In Press). Gait is now well established as a biometric capable of recognising individuals by the way they walk (Cunado *et al.*, 2002). Just as the iris of the eye or exterior structure of the ear have been shown to be unique to individuals, gait recognition can be achieved using computer vision to record the spatio-temporal pattern of a walking person. However, gait analysis and recognition techniques currently require a subject to walk within a

defined space, and may not be suited to the free roaming, user-centered approach envisioned by the authors.

5.2 Output: Feasibility Matrix

In order to assess their potential in this context, the authors constructed a matrix of possible output methods for initial prototyping (Table 5).

Method of Displaying Movement	Sub-category	Function	Advantages	Limitations	Possible Design Strategy or Issues
Light	LED	Flash, change colour, intensity, refraction.	Low energy requirements, long lasting, several colours available, cheap.	Colours limited to red green, blue, yellow.	All over body glow or more focussed site on body?
	Halogen	As above	Bright.	Prone to bulb breakage.	As above
	Laser	As above	Focussed beam over long projection distances. Bright.	Energy intensive, relatively expensive.	As above.
	LCD	Display graphical, numerical, symbolic or pictorial data.	Versatility in terms of what can be displayed.	Relatively expensive, complicated, prone to breakage. Requires hardware to operate. Two colour display.	Where to position display?
Electricity		Used to make something work e.g. light. Electric shock. Change in voltage, current, power output, frequency of current if pulsed.	Low voltage can be generated by body movement e.g. pelvis, footfall or breathing movements.	Cannot see, hear, smell, or taste electricity. Requires a generator.	Covered by other options i.e. electricity is generated by the movement. Mini lightning bolts? Possible to feel electricity.
Sound		Change in volume, pitch or frequency, also ambience, timbre, percussivity etc	Linked with dance, display of movement, fashion and expression of emotion.	Volume may be difficult; energy intensive.	Music, sound, rhythm?
Heat		Change in temperature.	As above	High heat levels may be difficult: energy intensive, relatively expensive.	Colour change via heat sensitive material?
Movement		Movement in x,y and or z. Reciprocating, linear and/or rotational movement.	Relatively easy to manufacture, may be cheap, many options.	Person already moving- object to move in interesting/appealing way.	Kinetic elements e.g. pedometer; ball bearings; movement of oil/ water within a wearable artefact?
Static/Friction		Produces heat, static charge.	Novel way of displaying movement.	Only visible from close by.	Artificial hairs, fibres stand on end depending on level of static
Microwave		Produces signals of varying frequency and/or magnitudes; vibration of atoms.	As above.	Cannot hear, see, smell, taste or touch.	Produces friction remotely i.e travels through the air.
Radiowave		Produces signals of varying frequency and/or magnitudes.	Novel way of displaying movement.	Cannot hear, see, smell, taste or touch.	Travels through the air. Bluetooth.
Infrared		Produces signals of varying frequency and/or magnitudes.	Novel way of displaying movement.	Expensive. Cannot hear, see, smell, taste or touch.	Invisible to the eye.

Table 5, PSD Output Mediums – Feasibility Matrix (Summary).

6. Conclusions

For the first in our PSD series, we have selected to use sonic output: music and rhythm have strong and long established associations with body movement, dance, fashion and the expression of emotion. Sound has three variables: amplitude, frequency, and pitch. Our design strategy is as follows: the PSD will be part garment/accessory, part sonic instrument; worn on the body with the facility to synthesise qualitative body movement and sound. We are experimenting with electric goniometers on the elbow or knee joints; accelerometers registering the rise and fall of the rib cage, kinetic elements worn on the trunk, shoulder or hips; and foot-pressure sensors. in order to generate sound. For future work, gait analysis and recognition techniques suggest possibilities where an ‘orchestra’ of moving bodies could perform together in a defined social space. Linking motion with sound will provide a possibility for wearers to experience their body moving in space in a different or heightened way via the fusion of kinesthesia and auditory sensation. Although socially generated, personal style cannot be imposed: it exists in the subtle tension between the expertise of originators and their fashionable copies. In the same manner that not all athletes are capable of becoming great because of genetics and less than ideal physiology and anatomy (Astrand et al, 2003), some users may be more ‘gifted’ in maximising the output of the device than others. Depending on the amount of practice and the ability of the wearer to learn how to get the most out of interacting with the device, an individual will develop a certain level of competence or even expertise (Moen, 2005). We anticipate that sounds could be generated and controlled via e.g. the swing of the pelvis, flex of elbow or knee, nuance of footstep. More precise or delicate sounds could be generated by the hands and fingers. We aim that the resulting accompaniment could be privately experienced in the moment via earpieces, ‘tuned’ to encompass different ambience of sound e.g. voice, chime, drum, strings and then saved, so that tracks could be superimposed over time until a composition is completed. Virtuoso fashion performers could strut, slink, jog, leap or run along the city’s streets, stairways, and pavements while creating their own dynamic body percussion. Movement would be stimulated and personally experienced through sound and rhythm by the wearer; but witnessed as ‘personal style’ by spectators, who would *see* the *sounds* as wearers walk the walk.....

“I am forced to cry for a “partition of movements” where to place my instruments – which are the human bodies – in a manner that is in absolute accordance with a white canvas for Bakst or a group of violins for Debussy. My

composition is even less simple because the human body does not possess just four strings but an infinite multitude of sensitive and expressive elements". Vaslav Nijinsky, in relation to 'Le Sacre du Printemps' (Cahusac, 1913).

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